

Unmasking the Plague: Exploring Corruption's Impediment to Zimbabwe's National Development and Growth

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Abstract

This study critiqued the pro-found consequences of corruption on national development in Zimbabwe, with a focus on its economic, political, and social dimensions. The materials for this paper were generated through secondary sources such as journals, books, book chapters, newspapers and internet sources while the content analysis and interrogation of the data was purely a critical one. Using such an approach, the study brings to light the complex web of corrupt practices and mechanisms that have become entrenched in Zimbabwe's institutions, systems, and culture. The revelations of the interrogation exhibits that corruption has amplified significantly to Zimbabwe's economic quiescence, political instability, and social fragmentation, with obliterating ramifications on the attainment of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030 and the second republic's 2030 agenda. This article makes the case that, ameliorating corruption is grievous for Zimbabwe's development prospects and propose a petition of policies and institutional reforms to combat corruption and promote transparency, accountability, and good governance. By demystifying the plague of corruption, this research aims to bequeath a more nuanced comprehension of the complex challenges facing Zimbabwe and to inform empirically-supported approaches for sustainable development and social transformation.

Keywords: *Corruption, national development, economic development, political instability, social fragmentation, good governance, Zimbabwe.*

Introduction

It is no longer a hyperbole to state that the news of politically induced corruption in Zimbabwe has heightened to stage where it has become a global concern. The bane has become a pervasive and deleterious force in present day Zimbabwe, subverting the country's development orbit and propagating poverty, economic hardships, inequality, and social injustice, (Chinodya, 2021). The mystery has become a ubiquitous and insidious phenomenon in Zimbabwe, permeating every facet of society and compromising the country's quest for development trajectories. The scourge of corruption has ravaged Zimbabwe's economy, political landscape, and social fabric, perpetuating human rights violations, inequality, and social fragmentation, (Jeche, 2022). Despite its calamitous consequences, corruption festers as a pernicious and deeply entrenched problem in Zimbabwe, with far-reaching impacts on the country's governance, economic growth, and human development at large.

Zimbabwe's corruption crisis is characterized by widespread bribery, embezzlement, nepotism, and cronyism, with those in positions of power frequently exploiting their authority for personal or group gain, (Jeche, 2022). The country's institutions, systems, and processes have been compromised, creating an environment conducive to corrupt shenanigans or practices. The consequences of corruption in Zimbabwe are desolate, with the country ranking among the poorest and most unscrupulous in the world, (World Bank, 2021). World Bank (2022) highlighted that its findings from 2020 Global Corruption Barometer (GCB) and the 2021 National Corruption Barometer (NCB) both confess that corruption is high and continues to intensify in Zimbabwe. Respondents from both organs, that is, GCB and NCB all agrees that corruption is alarming in the country percentiles at 75% and 82% respectively. It is also interesting to note that, according to Corruption Perception Index (CPI), Zimbabwe is ranked 149 out of 180 countries in the CPI, indicating a high level of perceived corruption in the public sector. With these high percentages and indexes at our disposal, it is imperative to ascertain Charamba (2015) who echoed that, 'Zimbabwe has lost the dazzling opulence which would

have driven her quest to development through corruption and cronyism since independence to date.

Since independence in 1980, Zimbabwe government has been zealous to the hurdle of national development but with little progress. Ncube, (2020) contends that, commitment by Zimbabwean government has manifested in the forging of various development plans at national level and the formulation of appropriate policies aimed at navigating the whole country to the aspired development. These development plans and policies, on paper, according to Ncube, (2020) were at each point in time, widely eulogized to be the answer to the problems that national development pose to the country. However, these policy agendas and frameworks remained “cosmetic labels” that failed to impact positively to heal the nation’s development illness due to irrationalities of suppression embedded in the government system. For instance, Anti-Corruption committee (ZACC); human rights defenders and whistleblowers work courageously to expose and combat corruption but to no avail, mainly due to the cancerous effects of corruption in the whole government system, (Jeche, 2022). Further to that, having dispensed all these plans and policies all the years, the nation still has not been able to accomplish the desired development due to corruption activities. Based on the contemporary observation, it seems to be the case that Zimbabwe is making breakthrough negatively. Debates and studies have identified corruption as encumbrance towards the realization of the country’s national development goals.

Envisioning Corruption

Corruption is an ethical and socio-political problem that varies from place to place, time-bounded and culture to culture. It is a global manifestation that affects developing, underdeveloped and developed states globally, (Chiweshe, 2022). It has caused a lot of misfortunes and occurs at all levels of governance in any given country. The scourge of corruption has filtered in almost every sector of the country, including religious fraternity. It (corruption) has hampered the economic, social and political development of the state and also has negative impacts on human rights, (Charamba et al, 2024). Corruption is variously described to include all acts where there is the abuse of public power for private gain, (Zakiuddin, 2019). Guillermo (2022) defines it as an anti-social behavior which entails

awarding improper privileges to oneself or cronies contrary to legal and moral norms and which impairs the capacity of the government to secure the welfare of all citizens. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) (2021) also delineates corruption as the maltreatment of mandate or trust for private benefit; and is an enticement indulged in not only by public officials but also by those in positions of trust or authority in both private enterprises and non-profit organizations. In simpler terms, corruption may be defined as the abuse of power, position or trust for personal or group benefit in a monetary or otherwise means.

The level and quandary of corruption is really endemic and has since reached an alarming stage in Zimbabwe's all development corridors. It has spread its wings to each and every corner of the country's economic sectors and has since been likened to cancer by many scholars, amongst them include, Gweru (2016); Chiweshe (2022), Ncube (2020) and Moyo (2020). Chiweshe (2022) argues that corruption is interwoven in all facets of daily lives in Zimbabwe and this places a serious responsibility especially on vulnerable and poor groups which constitutes greater part of populace in the country. Other studies have also confirmed how endemic corruption is in Zimbabwe, with the following incidences showcasing an unequivocal testimony:

- ❖ The 2023 KPMG Africa Fraud Barometer indicated that Zimbabwe, Nigeria, Kenya and South Africa (RSA) account for over 80% of all fraud type cases reported in the continent, (KPMG 2023).
- ❖ Newspapers such as 'The Standard; Newsday; The Herald all reported about, 'Mnangagwa Command Agriculture Scandal' This scandal occurred in 2016 where millions of United States dollars went missing and no one was questioned or brought to book for accountability to that.
- ❖ Zesa Scandal by Samuel Undenge in 2016 where the said Minister abused office and millions of United States dollars for the said bills went missing to no trace. Millions were abused at the expense of the whole nation and that alone paralyzed the economic performance of the country with regards to energy provision, (The Standard 2016; Newsday 2016, The Daily news 2016, The Independent, 2016).
- ❖ Air-Port Road scandal where allegations emerged that Moyo had bribed the government officials to secure the contract. It was further revealed that the project's costs had been

grossly inflated, and the contractor had diverted funds meant for the project to his own personal accounts. The Air-port road scandal is widely, seen as an example of the pervasiveness of corruption and cronyism that has plagued Zimbabwe's government and economy for decades, (Daily news, Newsday, The herald, The Standard, Bulawayo24 etc.).

- ❖ Covid-19 Obadiah Moyo \$ 60 million United States dollars Scandal where the then Health minister was accused of flouting procurement procedures and accepting bribes from the suppliers of Covid-19 masks, (Africa Report, Daily news, Newsday, The article etc.).
- ❖ Diamond Trade 2011- The then Finance Minister Tendai Biti claimed that at least \$1billion United States dollars in diamond related revenue owed to the national treasury remains unaccounted for and this has since paralyzed the government's pursuit for economic development, (Gweru, 2016; Moyo, 2020; Ncube, 2020; Chiweshe, 2022; The Standard, Daily news; Newsday etc.).
- ❖ The missing \$15 Billion United States dollars-through illicit financial flows: In December, 2015, the then Reserve Bank Governor in Zimbabwe noted that the country has lost an estimated US\$500million through illicit financial flows. In the following year, the then President of the Republic, R.G Mugabe in an interview to mark his birthday noted and admitted that Zimbabwe had lost US\$15 Billion from proceeds of diamond mining in the country, (Moyo,2020; Ncube, 2020, Chiweshe, 2020, Gweru, 2016).
- ❖ The "Gold Mafia: The Finale" and "Gold Mafia: The Zimbabwe Connection": This documentary authored in 2022 implicated several high-ranking officials, including politicians and security forces, in the illicit gold trade. The documentary series authored by Al Jazeera's investigative unit unmasked a complex web of corruption and money laundering involving gold smuggling, by top notch-politicians, and business people in Zimbabwe and most of them aligned to the first family, (Africa Report, Daily news, Newsday, The article etc).

The incidents above clearly unburden oneself that Zimbabwe has spontaneously lost billions of United States dollars that could have been utilized to finance varying planned developments

endeavors or projects that sought to benefit the country but rather the lost billions fell into the hands of few political elites and those strongly connected to such people. Such a scenario was further compounded by the report on High Level Panel (HLP) on illicit financial flows from Africa which was presented on the 24th African Union (AU) summit in Addis Ababa that outlines how threatening are such activities to Africa's development agenda and Zimbabwe is not spared. For Zimbabwe in particular, the continual leakages of millions of US dollars through illicit financial flows as previously laid bare by the Al Jazeera investigative journalists in 2022, pose a serious threat to the country for the attainment of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030 as per UN deadline and 2030 agenda as defined by the second republic.

In the presence of this incriminating evidence on corruption in Zimbabwe, it is humiliating to see the government through its enforcement agents run after those who are exposing such corrupt shenanigans and detain them. For example one prominent journalist by name Hopewell Chin'ono who unmasked the corrupt deals involving the former health minister (Obadiah Moyo) on Covid-19 funds was detained in 2020 for reporting such, (The Article, 2020; Daily News, 2020 and Africa Report, 2020). It is becoming more worrisome for most of the Zimbabwean populace since they are now butt of the joke or ridic and always humiliated in the region. For instance public utterances by Fikile Mbalula (ANC Secretary General) in 2023 that Zimbabweans are burdening our social services provision to our citizens especially in the health fraternity, (Newsday, 2023; Bulawayo24, 2023 and The Herald, 2023). Such utterances are also said in Botswana and Zambia, to a greater extent, the utterances are true but morally and psychologically damaging. If corruption was not all that rampant in Zimbabwe as confessed by the above incidences, the government could have revamped its health system using all these missed millions if not billions United States dollars and ultimately protect its citizens from been ridics across the region.

To that note, it is no longer an embellishment that, those who are not connected strongly to the top officials in government, those not politically connected and those not connected to the first family are becoming more susceptible to the caprices of authoritarianism in Zimbabwe.

Current Legal and Institutional Reforms on Corruption in Zimbabwe

Whilst constant efforts to reduce corruption and improve governance are necessary and desirable, there can be no meaningful results unless attention is also given to the governance capacities required for accelerating and sustaining development, (Hun et al 2020). The challenge for developing nations like Zimbabwe trying to devise institutional reform and anti-corruption strategies is to adopt the appropriate strategies from other countries' experiences and modify them to create feasible governance reform agendas appropriate and feasible for their own circumstances (Khan 2021). Anti-corruption reforms in Zimbabwe may be classified into two categories, namely legal reforms and institutional reforms.

Legal reforms pertain to the alterations made to national legislation in order to address offences associated with corruption were put in place. Since Zimbabwe gained its independence in 1980, the parliament has approved numerous acts of parliament that serve as different legislative frameworks. These include, among other things, the Zimbabwe constitution and the Criminal Law (Codification and Reform) Act.

Unfortunately, these pieces of legislation do not specifically define corruption. It is generally defined in its simplest form as the abuse of public office for private gain (World Bank, 2017). The code seems to define acts by which there is no disclosure to the principal or acts where there is deceit towards the principal as corrupt acts. It defines two types of acts as corruption. The first one is where there is no disclosure of transaction to the principal- Section 172 and the second one is where the no disclosure of a personal interest in the transaction to the principal – Section 173.

However Section 174 of the code covers situations which involve public officers. It states that if a public officer does anything contrary or inconsistent with his duties as a public officer or omits to do anything which it is her duty to carry out as a public officer, for purposes of showing favour to any person, then he or she would have committed an offence. What is striking in these sections is that they cover corrupt activities committed by agents against their principals and also persons holding public offices. Prior 2004 corruption activities were charged under the common law as bribery. This is now covered under section 170. These sections should be viewed as complementing each other to cover both public officials and non-public officials.

Sadly in most cases these legal provisions seem more of cosmetic displays which should exist as requirement only to please general populace. Their effectiveness is questionable especially when political figures or those who are connected to the political entities are involved in corruption activities. This is evidenced by non-investigation of cases like ‘Mnangagwa Command Agriculture Scandal’, (Jeche 2022).

The institutional framework on the other hand involves the establishment of various institutions either in terms of the constitution or to curb corruption. Chapter 13 of the Zimbabwe Constitution introduced the institutions to combat corruption and crime. This was necessitated by the fact that the costs of corruption on economic, social and political development had become increasingly evident in the previous government’s reign of office, (Chiweshe 2022). There was also realization that the political, social and economic development of a nation depends on its public sector control. The best thing developing countries should practice is govern the country with competent, committed and honest individuals directing institutions, (Ncube 2020).

The established institutions include the Zimbabwe Anti-Corruption Commission and the National Prosecuting Authority which work hand in glove with the police. Together they are meant to form a closely knit network and complement each other in their duties to combat corruption. However in reality these institutions are always competing and fingering each other for their short comings in the fight to eradicate corruption. For example the Prosecutor General Loice Matanda-Moyo admitted that there tended to be a degree of inter-agency rivalry and sometimes investigators were not cooperating and sometimes there was serious lack of coordination between investigation and prosecution (The Herald Newspaper, 2024). Various other factors come into play when an assessment of each of the organ’s ability to effectively play its part is done. These range from lack of resources, lack of commitment by both the government and the institutions personnel. This has led to the institutions for combating corruption becoming the nation’s corruption hubs.

Chapter 12 of the Constitution provides for the establishment of independent commissions supporting democracy. These include the Zimbabwe Electoral Commission, the Zimbabwe

Gender Commission, the Zimbabwe Media Commission and the Zimbabwe Human Rights Commission

These commissions play a crucial role in the fight against corruption. However they are, frequently so politicized that they are ineffective. They may be so beholden to their political masters that they dare not investigate even the most corrupt government officials; they may lack the power to prosecute; and they may be poorly staffed, (Pope and Vogl, 2019). Consequently there would be little point in setting up such Commissions if the Commissions are not going to be effective. It is essential that the Constitution should ensure that Commissions are truly independent, both in terms of appointment and freedom from interference with their functions from other arms of government organs. They should be answerable to Parliament and not the Executive and should receive enough funding to enable them to perform their functions independently.

The Insidious Effects of Corruption on National Developmental Trajectory

Corruption as noted earlier in this writing usually manifests from a miscarriage of justice in any given society. At its core, corruption is a complex issue with multifaceted causes, driven by a toxic mix of factors including power imbalances, economic inequalities, lack of transparency and accountability, and cultural norms that tolerate or even encourage unethical behavior, (Ekeh, 2024). From systemic flaws and institutional weaknesses to personal greed and moral decay, the roots of corruption run deep, making it a strenuous scourge to obliterate. Understanding the underlying causes of the bane is crucial to developing effective strategies for prevention, mitigation, and ultimately, a more just equitable and sustainable society. It is also important to note that, people do not indulge in corrupt practices because they like doing so, but it is often the only option, in particular where the system is already crumbled. Some of the main causes are discussed below:

Political Instability- refers to a situation where a country's political system is characterized by uncertainty, conflict, change and unpredictability. All this according Ncube, (2020) can manifest in various ways such as frequent changes in government, political unrest (protests, or violence), power struggles between different groups or individuals, weak or ineffective institutions, social unrest, ethnic or religious tensions and last but not least threats to democracy

or human rights. In the context of Zimbabwe, political instability has been a persistent challenge and continuously eroding the decades of development in all facets of life today. Zimbabwe's history of political instability has led to a culture of corruption and patronage. Political instability creates an environment where individuals and groups jockey for power, leading to frequent changes in government policies and leadership thereby creating uncertainty allowing corrupt individuals and cartels to exploit the situation for personal gain, (Messick, 2021). The instability in political sphere always foster a culture of patronage and clientelism where political leaders end up rewarding the loyal supporters with job, contracts, tenders and other benefits regardless of merits. In Zimbabwean scenario, the issuance of tenders and contracts to controversial political elites such as Tagwirei; Chivhayo and others has become topical and continue to dismantle the political spheres and country at large economically as reported in most sections of the media in the country. Chivhayo scandals include ZESA tender, 2012; Gwanda Solar project, 2015; Zimbabwe Power Company, 2016; The Starlink issue etcetera. These incidents of political connectedness in awarding tenders and contracts dubiously, has since created an environment of insecurity and fear thereby leading to increased corruption as individuals seek to protect themselves and their interests at the expense of general populace, (Messick 2021). It has become a norm in Zimbabwe that the political instability has tremendously undermined numerous institutions, making it a daunting task to hold its integral leaders accountable for their behavior and actions, thereby creating conducive corruption environment.

Economic Conditions- In the context of Zimbabwe, economic crisis has contributed to corruption in various ways, including; hyperinflation, currency fluctuations, food shortages, poverty, lack of resources, smuggling and black markets, patronage and cronyism etcetera. Poverty, unemployment, and economic hardships have driven general populace to engage in corrupt activities as a means of survival. According to World Bank (2022), 6.1 million people (38% of the population) is living in extreme poverty, defined as surviving on less than \$1.90 a day. Poverty scenario in Zimbabwe has limit the majority to access education, job opportunities, and other resources and this has led individuals to turn into corrupt shenanigans as a coping mechanism. Due to the poverty prevailing circumstances, most individuals are

becoming vulnerable to the vagaries of corruption such as exploitation and bribery, (Chiweshe, 2022).

Unemployment –Whether unemployment is in form of frictional, structural, cyclical or seasonal relates to a situation whereby people who are able and willing to work cannot find jobs, (Messick, 2021). In other words, it may mean a measure of the number of people who are actively seeking work but are unable to find jobs. Unemployment or insufficient employment opportunities are a major inducement for corruption. In Zimbabwe, unemployment rate has reached over 90% and this means that, out of desperation and lack of other opportunities, most of the unemployed individuals especially youths are likely to be vulnerable to corruption vagaries, (Nyoni, 2021). Also due to lack of income, the unemployed suffer financial constraints thereby making them more susceptible to corruption shenanigans.

Public Admiration for Unethically Acquired Wealth - Many people in Zimbabwean society, even in churches today do not care anymore about how people acquire their wealth. Instead, they worship and shower praises on known crooks who make heavy donations to them and ridicule the honest but rich who cannot afford to spray and make heavy donations with their hard-earned cash, (Chitando, 2023). The Chivhayo scenario in Zimbabwe is the case in point where the accused is seen splashing money, houses and cars to various people without traces on how he got that money. Also with the zeal to get rich easily, some individuals get into dubious activities and immoral actions like rituals which have become the order of the day, (Jeche 2022). Corruption is so endemic in Zimbabwean system that it is proving near impossible to eradicate. The irony is that, without eradicating corruption in the Zimbabwean system, it would be very difficult for the country to witness any form of sustainable national development.

Zimbabwe's Corruption Conundrum: Underlying Factors

Corruption has far-reaching impacts on national development, affecting various aspects of a country's growth and prosperity. Some of the keys impacts of corruption are discussed below:

Economic Impacts

Corruption itself distorts the allocation of resources, leading to inefficient investments and projects that benefit corrupt individuals rather than the broader economy. The cost of doing business in a corrupt set up always increase as companies are obliged to pay bribes or engage in other corrupt activities to fully operate, (Moyo, 2020). Talent emigration is another set-back posed by corruption. It drives off the talented individuals out of the country, reducing the workforce's skillsets and general productivity. Inflation is also a by-product of corruption, since most of the corrupt activities drive up the prices and this shun foreign investors from investing in the country, (Todaro et al, 2006). Country's economic competitiveness is being reduced to corrupt activities, making it harder to attract investment opportunities and required talent in the country.

Political Impacts

According to Masunungure, (2020) corruption in most cases lead to cronyism, where political connections are rewarded with jobs, tenders, contracts, or other benefits while others are shunned from enjoying the same benefits. Accountability is also undermined as those in power or office of authority use their positions to protect themselves and their allies from scrutiny. These power bearers also have tendencies to ignore or manipulate the existing systems to fit what they want or to benefit themselves alone at the expense of the general populace. Political polarization is another by-product of corruption, where citizens become increasingly divided along partisan lines. In Zimbabwe such a scenario has led to decreased compromise, increased extremism, social unrest, decreased civic engagement, increased conflict, decreased trust, increased gridlock and decreased cooperation, (Chiweshe, 2020).

Social Impacts

Due to great manipulation of laws (corruption) by the elites or political office bearers, there has been a gross reduction in accessing quality social services such as health, education, water and sanitation related, (Chiweshe, 2020). Because of corrupt tendencies by those in office of power, there has been increase in inequalities and social injustice in the country. Human rights violations (particularly the right to education, healthcare and fair standard of living) has become the order of the day and most of the civic organizations championing human rights in

the country were also de-registered, (Ncube, 2020). Corruption as in case of Zimbabwe according to Masunungure, (2020) has also led to social unrest, protests, and even conflict, as people demand change and accountability. Charamba, (2015) also resonates that, gender inequality is a child born out of corruption, since corruption itself disproportionately affects women and girls, perpetuating inequality and discrimination, thereby causing fragmentation of the society.

Environmental Impacts

Corruption has significant environmental impacts that impede development and sustainability. The bane of corruption fuels illegal logging, deforestation, and land degradation, leading to loss of biodiversity and ecosystem disruption. With high levels of corruption in most parts of Zimbabwe, World Bank (2020) highlighted that, industries are operating at will, dumping waste and pollutants in waterways, thereby threatening human health and aquatic ecosystems. The plague of corruption also through political elites has the capacity to weaken environmental laws and enforcement, allowing polluters to operate with impunity, (Masunungure, 2020). Alarming vulnerability to natural disasters by allowing unsafe construction and land use practices is another problem posed by corrupt system of the country. All these activities by those in power and authority surely undermines the effort to embrace climate change in the country since operating industries belongs to them, for they prioritize profits over sustainability.

Conclusion

It is important to note that corruption has a multiplier effect, and its impacts can be far-reaching and intergenerational, hence addressing it, is crucial for achieving desired sustainable development and improving the lives of citizens in the country. Labeling corruption as a scourge of Zimbabwe's socio-economic development is not enough but rather it has become a cancer threatening the existence of the country as a political, economic and social entity. It is therefore imperative that all hands must be on the deck in the anti-corrupt struggle. In order to curb this bane on a local setting, it is the submission of this paper that the journey to a corruption free society starts in the home, where parents should teach their children right from wrong, set a good example, and intervene when necessary.

Secondly, at schools (school socialization process), teachers who are bestowed with the parenting tasks on the children and youths should as well impact good morals academically and otherwise so as to endeavor best nurturing exercises divulge from corrupt activities. The age-old adage “Spare the rod and spoil the child” still holds true, but teachers must discipline with care, avoiding intimidation to foster a positive learning environment.

Recommendations

Having said the above remedies to cure corruption at household level, in a broader perspective, the Zimbabwean government should carefully consider the following for it to achieve both Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030 and its Agenda 2030 (as defined by the second republic).

- ❖ **Strengthening of Institutions-** Zimbabwean government without fail must establish several independent, biting and effective institutions to fight corruption activities in the country. Institutions such as Zimbabwe Anti-Corruption Commission (ZACC) must be well funded and resourced so as to avoid temptations of accepting bribes in the corridors of the country’s economic hubs.
- ❖ **Non-partiality Enforcement of laws-** The Zimbabwe government must make sure that those law enforcement agents in place should apply the regulations in a professional and consistent manner without bias towards high profile office bearers in any sector. In Zimbabwe, those who are politically connected even if they are found on the wrong side of the law, they are allowed to walk free. For instance, the then Minister of Health Obadiah Moyo who was accused of squandering Covid-19 funds totaling USD\$60 million, was not charged to date because of the said connection to the first family as reported in most social media sections. So for the country to prosper in the fight against corruption, the laws and regulations must be applied without partiality or any given exception. Responsible authorities must by all means desist from “**Catch and Release**” style of doing things so as to parade transparency.
- ❖ **Education and Enlightenment-** Educating the public about the consequences of corruption and promoting a culture of integrity is idle to achieve a corrupt free environment. It is the duty or mandate of the government and the civic organizations to

put hands together and educate the general populace about the dire effects of corruption in their localities and country at large. It is also a submission of this write up that, if possible “Corruption” must be taken as a subject from primary to tertiary level or be included as a compulsory element in the curriculum so that the teaching sinks deep in the minds of many. Civic engagement and participation in the anti-corruption advocacy nation-wide must be encouraged rather than de-registering other partners who are vital in the fight against corruption.

- ❖ **Whistle-Blower Protection and Support-** By empowering whistleblowers, Zimbabwe can make significant strides in the fight against corruption. Since whistleblowers can expose corrupt activities, provide evidence for corrupt acts, hold leaders accountable for their actions, promote transparency, can advance justice etcetera, such is a milestone to be reached in Zimbabwean situation. In Zimbabwe whistleblowers face a lot of challenges which includes retaliation, lack of protection, fear of reprisal, limited access to information among others. It is therefore important for Zimbabwe to consider strengthening whistleblower protection laws and mechanisms, ensure access to information and evidence, and provide safe channels of reporting corrupt activities and promoting a culture of transparency and accountability. The government must applaud and credit the work of whistleblowers rather than setting up repression laws. The responsible government must focus on empowering and protecting individuals who come forward to report wrong doings or unethical behaviors both in private and public domains, For instance Zimbabwe’s well known corruption whistleblower journalist Hopewell Chin’ono who unearthed the Covid-19 scandal involving Obadiah Moyo has since ran away after initially detained for reporting that and now he is based in Switzerland due to repressive laws in the country.
- ❖ **Wealth Accumulation Evaluation or Lifestyle Audit-** In the context of fighting corruption, it involves examining an individual’s lifestyle to identify any discrepancies between their income and expenditure, and detect any potential corrupt activities or some discrepancies. This may entails income and expenditure, asset declaration, conflict of interest, travel and entertainment, financial transactions, living standards evaluations, business relationships and gifts and hospitality among others. This exercise

helps the responsible authority to detect unexplained wealth, expose financial discrepancies, uncover conflicts of interests, deters corrupt behavior, and promotes accountability, foster public trust as well as supporting asset recovery mechanisms. By conducting lifestyle audits, individuals and institutions can demonstrate their commitment to transparency and accountability, ultimately helping to prevent and detect corruption early at any given set up.

- ❖ Lastly, improvements in socio-economic and political life should be improved. Job opportunities should be created because this will keep the minds of the youths busy and free from corrupt tendencies. Workers' salaries should not only be paid as at when due, but the workers should be paid a living wage that sustain and motivate them to shun corrupt practices. If these measures are taken into consideration, together with a general re-orientation of the Zimbabwean people, the country can begin to take the necessary steps towards achieving socio-economic development.

Above all, there should be a strong political will (the commitment and determination of a country's leaders to drive development and implement policies that benefit the nation), with clearly defined vision and development goals; effective governance and institutions; consensus building and stakeholders collaboration; transparency and accountability among others for Zimbabwe to realize its developmental trajectories.

References

Charamba, G., Chikwati, T. and Chidarikire, M. (2024): *Gender Equality and Women Economic Empowerment: An Analysis of ZAOGA FIF Church in Masvingo Province, Zimbabwe*. Available at: <https://doi.org/zenodo.12524861>. Accessed on 30 June 2024.

Charamba, G. (2015): *Influence of Religion on Gender Equality and Women Empowerment: An Analysis of ZAOGA Church in Masvingo City*. Unpublished Master's Thesis, Department of Development Studies, Lupane State University.

Chiweshe, M.K. (2022) Foucault, Power and Abuse of Authority: Towards Sociology of Corruption in Zimbabwe. Available at: www.tni.org/files/download. Accessed on: 24 June 2024.

Chinodya, S. (2021). Harvest of Thorns, Satirize political corruption in Zimbabwe. Accessed on: 24 June 2024.

Ekeh, F.I. (2024) Corruption: The Scourge of National Development in Nigeria. African Journal of Social and Behavioral Sciences, Vol 14 Number 2. Accessed on: 20 July 2024.

Guillemot, W. (2022) Corruption-The World's Big C: Institute of Economic Affairs, London.

Hove C (2018) Bones and Shadow: A critique on Corruption and Political oppression in Zimbabwe. Accessed on: 24 June 2024.

International Monetary Fund (IMF) (2021): The Evil of Corruption. Geneva. Accessed on: 15 July 2024.

Gweru, C. (2020) Corruption: A Cancer eating Zimbabwe. The Herald. Available at: <http://www.herald.co.zw/corruption-a-cancer-eating-zimbabwe>. Accessed on: 20 July 2024.

Jeche. V. R. (2022) Corruption in Zimbabwe: A Crisis of Governance. African Journal of Politics. Accessed on 20 June 2024.

Moyo, S. (2020) Unpacking the Corruption Nexus in Zimbabwe. Accessed on: 24 June 2024.

Moyo, G. (2020) Impact of Corruption on Democracy in Zimbabwe. Accessed on: 24 June 2024.

Masaya, M. (2017) Corruption and Economic growth in Zimbabwe. Accessed on: 24 June 2024.

Masunungure, E. (2020) The Anatomy of Political Predation: Leaders, Elites and Coalitions in Zimbabwe. Available at: <http://dlprog.org/publications>. Accessed on: 01 June 2024.

Messick, R. (2021) "When you fight Corruption, it Fights back": The Global Anti-Corruption Blog. Accessed on: 20 June 2024.

Mupanda, C. (2019) An Analysis of Corruption in Zimbabwe's mining sector. Accessed on; 24 June 2024.

Ncube, M.J. (2020) Analysis of Transparency and Accountability in Land Sector Governance in Zimbabwe. Available at: <http://Kubatana>. Kubatana.netdna-cdn.com. Accessed on: 20 July 2024.

Nhede, N.T. (2013) Devolution of power and effective governance The Zimbabwean constitutional debate African Journal of Public Affairs Volume 6 (4).

Pope, J. and Vogl, F. (2000) Making Anticorruption Agencies More Effective, IMF Finance and Development Magazine, Vol 37 (2).

World Bank. (2017). World development report: Governance and the law. New York: Oxford University Press. Spotlight 1. p77

Zakiuddin, A. (2015) Corruption in Bangladesh: An Analytical and Sociological Study. Available at: <http://upanl.un.org/documents>. Accessed on: 24 July 2024.

Newspapers

Africa Report, 17 August 2020.

Daily news, 16 May 2016. Available on <https://dailynews.co.zw>. Accessed on: 24 July 2024

Daily news, 23 June 2023. Available on <https://dailynews.co.zw>. Accessed on: 24 July 2024

Newsday, 28 June 2023. Available on <http://www.newsday.org.co.zw>. Accessed on: 24 July 2024.

The Herald, 13 May 2024. Available on <https://www.herald.co.zw/editorial-comment-collaboration-between-zacc-npa-will-bear-fruit/>. Accessed on: 10 September 2024

The Standard, July 2019. Available on: <https://www.thestandard.co.zw>. Accessed on 24 July 2024.

Zimbabwe Independent, 29 March 2012. ZESA Bill Scam: A mirror on the Abuse of Power. Available at: <http://www.theindependent.co.zw/2012/03/29>. Accessed on: 24 July 2024.